

A Swiss Calendar Maker in Colonial America:

The Life and Work of Johannes Tobler (1696-1765) between Appenzell Ausserrhoden and South Carolina

by David Aragai

Introduction

Johannes Tobler was a self-taught mathematician and astronomer. He published the first “Appenzeller Kalender” in 1721, an astronomical almanac in the style of the then popular genre. This almanac was the first periodical of Appenzell Ausserrhoden and is still issued today. After Tobler became a magistrate in the council of Appenzell Ausserrhoden, he found himself on the losing side of an internal conflict, called the *Landhandel*. As a result, he emigrated with his family and nearly two hundred citizens of Switzerland to South Carolina in 1736/37. After several years in which he built a new livelihood and became Justice of the Peace in his new home town of New Windsor by the Savannah River, he again started to issue almanacs, this time in English and under his anglicized first name of John. With “The South Carolina and Georgia Almanack” from 1752 onwards, Tobler published the first almanac in the southern part of the British Colonies in America. Furthermore, he served as philomath (calculator of the *Calendarium*) for a number of other American almanacs. He died in New Windsor in 1765.

This article tells the story of Johannes Tobler’s life between Switzerland and Colonial America. Of special interest will be his calendar-making. Taking into consideration the source material from

Figure 1: Portrait of Johannes Tobler which was part of his obituary in the “Appenzeller Kalender” for the year 1767. Courtesy: State Library of Appenzell Ausserrhoden, Trogen.¹

the Swiss Confederacy as well as from America—written in German as well as in English—the text tells Tobler’s life as a transnational biography.² This also includes taking a closer look at his life in New Windsor as a slave owner and colonization agent in an area where

¹ Note that the obituary including the portrait only was printed in a special issue of the almanac, not in the general edition for the year 1767.

² In this sense, this article seeks to be a contribution to a transnational history of Switzerland, laid out in: Pierre Eichenberger, et al., “Beyond Switzerland: Reframing the Swiss Historical Narrative in Light of Transnational History,” *Traverse: Zeitschrift für Geschichte* 1 (2017): 137-52.

Figure 2: Map of Appenzell Auserroden (shown in red) from 1740 by Gabriel Wälder, Tobler's successor as a calendar maker. Courtesy: State Library of Appenzell Auserroden, Trogen.

Native Americans lived. As an important source, the article uses Tobler's own autobiographical writing to tell his story.

The Self-made Mathematician

Johannes Tobler's autobiographical writing includes a piece about his origin and upbringing in rural Eastern Switzerland. It appeared in English in an issue of his "The South-Carolina Almanack" for the year 1755, printed in 1754:

"I am born a Switzer, of the Canton of Appenzell, born in the Parish of Rehtobel, in the Year 1696, the 3d of September. My parents sent me early to School, wherein I learned to read, write and a little cyphering, the last whereof I have afterwards quite forgotten. Even from my Youth I had a Mind and Inclination for Arts and Sciences; but my beloved Parents were of Opinion, that nobody could learn any Art or Science, except in travelling into foreign Countrys, to which I had no Inclination."³

Tobler was born into a well-off burgher family in Cholenrüti, a hamlet in the parish of Rehetobel. His father was a cloth-manufacturer and farmer, this being the predominant occupations in eighteenth century Appenzell Ausserrhoden. The factory was right next to the Tobler's house. The manufacturers bought raw materials from local merchants and sold the finished products back to them. This being such a successful business model that several merchant dynasties emerged in the region and amassed great wealth. First among them were the Zellweger family from the neighboring parish of Trogen. This economic model created a unique decentralized landscape of hamlets, farmsteads, and single houses over the hills of Appenzell Ausserrhoden with rather small towns. It is a distinct feature, for which the canton is still known today.⁴

³ Johannes Tobler, "To the Respective honourable Reader," *The South-Carolina Almanack, For the Year of our Lord 1755* 3 (1754): without pagination.

⁴ Hanspeter Ruesch, *Lebensverhältnisse in einem frühen schweizerischen Industriegebiet: sozialgeschichtliche Studie über die Gemeinden Trogen, Rehetobel, Wald, Gais, Speicher und Wolfhalden des Kantons Appenzell Ausserrhoden im 18. und frühen 19. Jahrhundert* (Basel: Helbing & Lichtenhahn, 1979), 21-67.

In 1718, Tobler married Anna Zellweger (1699-1768) from Gais. She was a member of the influential family, although from a “lesser” branch of the clan. Nevertheless, this is a hint of the Tobler family’s rather high standing in the Appenzell Ausserrhoden society.⁵ Anna and Johannes started a family and had ten children altogether. Eventually, Johannes Tobler took over the family business in Cholenrüti. It is a remarkable deviation in the seemingly predetermined course of Tobler’s life that he became a self-taught mathematician and layman astronomer by studying books and that, in this capacity, he edited the first ever printed almanac in Appenzell Ausserrhoden.⁶ Tobler was the philomath of the “Appenzeller Kalender”, which means that he calculated the *Calendarium*. He describes his journey towards this feat as follows:

“In the Year 1719, I found some Delight in making Sun-Dials; but I saw that a good Deal of the Arithmetick was required to such a Performance, I procured therefore a Book of Arithmetical Instructions, which I soon brought into my Memory. Upon this I found very little Difficulty in making the said Sun-Dials, and also in the other Parts of the Mathematicks, and all this without any Instructions, or Direction of anybody. By the Music & musical Instruments, especially the Organ, I found many pleasant Hours, and thus collected my Thoughts again together. After this I had most Desire and Inclination for the Astronomy, and I was soon enabled to perform some of the Operations.”⁷

The “Appenzeller Kalender” was only one of many almanacs circulating in Eastern Switzerland at the time. The other almanacs came from places such as Basel, Bern, Swabia, Wuerttemberg, or Bavaria and had already been popular in the seventeenth century with the general public. They were not reserved for a rich or well-educated strata of society. The affordable almanacs were, apart from Bibles, hymnals, and other religious writings, the only printed

⁵ Heidi Eisenhut, “Wunderlich kommt mir die Baute vor.” *Der Fünfeckpalast in Trogen und die Familie Zellweger* (Schwellbrunn: Appenzeller Verlag, 2019), 164-470.

⁶ Lukas Boser, “Volksaufklärung und sozialer Aufstieg: Johannes Tobler, ein Appenzeller Kalendermacher im 18. Jahrhundert,” *Appenzellische Jahrbücher* 146 (2019): 19-27.

⁷ Tobler, “Respective Reader,” without pagination.

Figure 3: Front Page of the first “Appenzeller Kalender” for the year 1722 with a portrait of Johannes Tobler. It includes a house organ, which he owned. Courtesy: State Library of Appenzell Ausserrhoden, Trogen.

material in ordinary early modern European households—newspapers did not become widespread until the beginning of the nineteenth century. Therefore, Johannes Tobler had to justify in the first issue of his “Appenzeller Kalender” why he had printed yet another almanac. It was, as he explained, because in the circulating almanacs, some solar and lunar eclipses were missing which he had been able to calculate.

Thus, the main aim of the new almanac was to give a more precise astronomical calendar to the reader.⁸

Tobler's calendars were a mixture of astronomical observations, astrological projections, and religious contents. This was typical for the genre and Tobler did copy a lot of the content of his first "Appenzeller Kalender" from a contemporary almanac from Bern, the *Rosiuskalender*. On a single calendar page, the length of the day, eclipses of the sun and moon, the phases of the moon, the star signs, a weather forecast, signs of the planets, biblical citations, and a religious figure for each day can be found. Sometimes, blank spaces are included for the user to write down personal appointments, etc. Over time and with the help of books he bought, Tobler calculated more and more of these contents specifically for the meridian of Appenzell Ausserrhoden.⁹

An almanac is more than just a calendar. In addition to the *Calendarium*, it contains a section called *Practica* (which translates as "application" from the Latin). There, tips about gardening and farming, lengthy articles on news topics, philosophical questions, faraway cultures and peoples, excerpts from books, poems, anecdotes, humorous episodes, advice for a pious life, healthcare, and much more could be found. In alignment with an early modern European world view, reports about supernatural sightings, astrological advisory, and a yearlong weather forecast could be found, giving the almanac an air of superstition and quackery. However, it would be hasty to dismiss the contents of the "Appenzeller Kalender" and other similar publications as unenlightened and untrue. Instead, it is more suitable

⁸ David Aragai, "Ferne Welten und ein Stück Heimat—Der Appenzeller Kalender wird 300 Jahre alt," *Appenzeller Kalender* 300 (2021): 53-62; David Aragai and Marcel Prohaska, *Der Appenzeller Kalender: Zeitmesser / Ratgeber / Kulturgut* (Schwellbrunn: Appenzeller Verlag, 2024), forthcoming; Rudolf Schenda, "Hinkende Botschaften? Zur Entwicklung und Bedeutung der schweizerischen Volkskalender," *Schweizerisches Archiv für Volkskunde* 92 (1996): 161-81; Johannes Tobler, "An den guenstigen Leser," *Appenzeller Kalender* 1 (1722): without pagination.

⁹ Holger Böning, "Aufgeklärte Kalendermacher aus dem Bauernstand—der Appenzeller Kalender und seine Herausgeber," in *Schreibkalender und ihre Autoren in Mittel-, Ost- und Ostmitteleuropa (1540-1850)*, ed. Klaus-Dieter Herbst and Werner Greiling (Bremen: Edition Lumière, 2018), 459-91; Klaus-Dieter Herbst, "Von Astronomie bis Volksaufklärung. Neue Forschungen und Perspektiven," in *Astronomie—Literatur—Volksaufklärung. Der Schreibkalender der Frühen Neuzeit mit seinen Text- und Bildbeigaben*, ed. Klaus-Dieter Herbst (Bremen: Edition Lumière, 2012), 15-44.

to see its contents as a lens on early modern perspectives on the world and all the things upon it. What is more, almanacs from the second half of the seventeenth century onwards, including the “Appenzeller Kalender,” educated people beyond religion and were thus part of an Enlightenment “from below.” Johannes Tobler had a strong interest in natural sciences, which resulted in lengthy articles about weather phenomena, natural disasters and their causes, and astronomical topics. Due to the strong distribution of the almanacs, their influence on public discourse should not be underestimated.¹⁰

Due to the lack of a printing press in Rehetobel, Tobler printed his first almanac in Lindau, a city on the other side of Lake Constance in Swabia.¹¹ Later almanacs were printed in Ulm and St. Gallen and bound in St. Gallen and Herisau. Until the middle of the eighteenth century, the absence of printing houses in rural Appenzell Ausserrhoden is explained by the fact that the canton had no cities back then (today the capital Herisau has become one). The authorities in Appenzell Ausserrhoden especially appointed a censorship committee for the new periodical, as was normal in early modern Switzerland.¹²

Back then, Appenzell Ausserrhoden was an independent dwarf state bound together with twelve other states into the loose Swiss Confederacy. Ausserrhoden was a democracy with strong oligarchic tendencies as few families—among them the aforementioned Zellwegers—ruled as voted representatives. Federalism held sway as the parishes enjoyed strong independence from the state. The male citizens could vote once a year during a public gathering called

¹⁰ Holger Böning, “Volksaufklärung und Kalender. Zu den Anfängen der Diskussion über die Nutzung traditioneller Volkslesestoffe zur Aufklärung und zu ersten praktischen Versuchen bis 1800,” in *Astronomie—Literatur—Volksaufklärung. Der Schreibkalender der Frühen Neuzeit mit seinen Text- und Bildbeigaben*, ed. Klaus-Dieter Herbst (Bremen: Edition Lumière, 2012), 183-200; Lukas Boser, “Life Histories,” in *A Cultural History of Education in the Age of Enlightenment*, ed. Daniel Tröhler (London: Bloomsbury Academic, 2020), 169-86; Norbert D. Wernicke, “... kurz, was sich in den Kalender schikt.” *Literarische Texte in Schweizer Volkskalendern von 1508 bis 1848. Eine Bestandesaufnahme* (Bremen: Edition Lumière, 2011), 11-72.

¹¹ Since 1805, Lindau belongs to Bavaria.

¹² Walter Schläpfer, *Pressegeschichte des Kantons Appenzell Ausserrhoden* (Herisau: Appenzeller Verlag, 1978), 8-23; Teresa Tschui, “Wie solche Figur zeigt.” *Der schweizerische Volkskalender als Bildmedium vom 17. bis zum 19. Jahrhundert* (Bremen: Edition Lumière, 2009), 231-43.

the *Landsgemeinde*, and in gatherings in their parishes called the *Kirchhöre*.¹³

Because of the success of his “Appenzeller Kalender,” as well as his standing as a male burgher, Johannes Tobler became eligible to be voted into public office. He was elected as counsellor of his parish in 1723, then promoted to the leader of this board in 1728—an office comparable to that of a mayor. In 1730, he was elected from the *Landsgemeinde* into the state government. Johannes Tobler’s career reached successful heights in a short amount of time.¹⁴

Leaving the Swiss Confederacy

The lives of Johannes Tobler and his young family would undoubtedly have continued their course further along the plotted line had it not have been for the *Landhandel*. This was an internal strife in Appenzell Ausserrhoden from 1731 to 1735, stopping just short of a civil war. The two parties of the conflict were dubbed the *Harten* (the hard ones) and the *Linden* (the mild ones). The *Linden* consisted of the Zellweger family and their followers, which included more or less the whole eastern part of Appenzell Ausserrhoden including Rehetobel—the border being the Sitter River. Consequentially, Johannes Tobler found himself in this camp of the conflict. The *Harten* consisted of the Wetter family from Herisau and their followers. They were also influential textile merchants and politicians in the western part of Appenzell Ausserrhoden, in many ways the mirror image of the Zellweger family.¹⁵

There was an old rivalry between the Zellweger and the Wetter families which had led to the splitting of Appenzell Ausserrhoden into two spheres of influence back in 1647, known as “the regiment in front of the Sitter” and “the regiment behind the Sitter.” This old rivalry

¹³ Peter Witschi, “Appenzell Ausserrhoden,” Historical Dictionary of Switzerland, last modified October 25, 2019, <https://hls-dhs-dss.ch/de/articles/007476/2019-10-25/>.

¹⁴ Karl Kern, “Johannes Tobler, Mathematicus und Politiker (1696-1765),” in *Geschichte der Gemeinde Rehetobel 1669-1969*, ed. Walter Schläpfer (Herisau: Appenzeller Verlag, 1969), 59-67.

¹⁵ Fabian Brändle, *Demokratie und Charisma: Fünf Landsgemeindekonflikte im 18. Jahrhundert* (Zurich: Chronos, 2005), 211-80.

flared up in 1714 when an agreement with neighboring St. Gallen over import duties was negotiated and signed by magistrates from the *Linden* but refused in hindsight by the *Harten*. This led to skirmishes, fights, and a show of force by the *Harten* in 1733, when they called for an unscheduled *Landsgemeinde* under the threat of force. With a majority vote they sacked all the magistrates from the *Linden* party—including Johannes Tobler—and took over the government. More skirmishes followed and one person was murdered in the village of Gais. The Rehetobel population voted once again for Tobler as their chief in 1733, but this was not accepted by the ruling party so he had to resign all his posts. The conflict officially ended with a trial of all the former magistrates of the *Linden*—one of them being Johannes Tobler.¹⁶

As a consequence, Tobler was fined heavily and subjugated to a house search where much of his library and belongings were confiscated. These included parts of his calendar work which must have hit him hard. However, in Tobler's recollections he names something else as the worst part of this whole affair:

“The worst that happen'd with me, was, that part of the Country People blam'd and scolded me very much, therefore I made Complaint to the Magistrate in the Year 1735, and desired Protection; and although I did believe, that their Oath obliged them to do it, I could not obtain it. At length I saw fresh Dangers like to befall me, I resolved to leave my native and beloved Country.”¹⁷

Not feeling safe anymore in Appenzell Ausserrhoden, Johannes Tobler decided to migrate to the English Colonies in North America, more specifically to South Carolina. This decision to head for America was made at an early stage of migration across the Atlantic Ocean and long before the height of the Swiss and European migration waves to the United States in the nineteenth century. So why South Carolina? Tobler began discussions with Bartholomäus Zuberbühler (1678-1738), who was a fellow *Linden* and the former priest of the parish of Teufen in

¹⁶ Johannes Tobler, *Beschreibung der Landesunruhen von 1732-1735* (Trogen: unpublished manuscript, ca. 1735), 1-38.

¹⁷ Tobler, “Respective Reader,” without pagination.

Appenzell Ausserrhoden. Zuberbühler had mainly been exonerated because he was a vocal opponent of the state-promoted mercenary service to France. Bartholomäus' son, Sebastian Zuberbühler, was, as a promoter and organizer, involved in the founding of the Swiss colony Purrysburg in the South Carolina backcountry and already lived there since 1734. He sought to recruit new, well-off colonists for the township which had been founded by Jean Pierre Pury (1675-1736) from Neuchâtel in 1731/32. Tobler and Zuberbühler decided to form a group to migrate collectively.¹⁸

By then, Tobler must also have been influenced in his decision by popular books about the topic; for example, "Detailed and Comprehensive Report about the Famous Territory of Carolina" from 1709 by the German author Joshua Kocherthal (1669-1719), "American Guide or a Short and Actual Description of the English Provinces in North America. Especially the Territory of Carolina" from 1711 by Johann Rudolf Ochs (1673-1749) of Basel or "Shortened Description of the Present State of South Carolina" from 1732 by the aforementioned Jean Pierre Pury. These books were propaganda pieces, promising freedom of conscience, full civil rights, a plot of land, and even free food for every Protestant male. They omitted anything negative, for example: the harsh conditions to build new settlements in the backcountry, the conflicts emerging thereby with the Indigenous population, or the unfamiliar hot and humid climate for people acclimatized to central Europe.¹⁹

Johannes Tobler wanted to have a look himself and together with his father, Ulrich (1670-1737), and his son, who was also named Ulrich (1723-1760), they went on a scouting mission to South Carolina in

¹⁸ The names Zuberbühler and Pury are written in different styles in the sources, like Zouberbuhler, Zuberbiller, Puri, Purry, etc. Walter Schläpfer, *Wirtschaftsgeschichte des Kantons Appenzell Ausserrhoden bis 1939* (Gais: Appenzell Ausserrhodische Kantonalbank, 1984), 75-7.

¹⁹ Heiko Diekmann, *Lockruf der Neuen Welt: Deutschsprachige Werbeschriften für die Auswanderung nach Nordamerika von 1680 bis 1760* (Göttingen: Universitätsverlag, 2005), 1-21 and 201-09; Josua Kocherthal, *Außführlich- und umständlicher Bericht von der berühmten Landschaft Carolina (...)* (Frankfurt am Main: Georg Heinrich Oehrling, 1709), 2-6; Jean Pierre Pury, *Description abrégée de l'état présent de la Caroline Méridionale* (Neuchâtel: Jacob Boyve, 1732), 1-36; Leo Schelbert, "In Praise of Carolina: Johann Rudolph Ochs's Americanischer Wegweiser of 1711," *Yearbook of German-American Studies* 1990 25 (1991): 109-29.

1735. Konrad Schoch and his wife Anna from Rehetobel and probably also other people joined the party. While Johannes returned to the Swiss Confederacy to pick up the rest of the family and put together a group of willing migrants, he meanwhile left his father and son in the town of Orangeburg where Ulrich senior received a land grant.²⁰

In order to encourage potential migrants to join settling in South Carolina, Johannes Tobler wrote a piece in similar fashion to the pamphlets mentioned above called “Brief Description of the New World, also called the Great Continent America” which he published in the “Appenzeller Kalender” for the year 1736. In it, he compares Carolina to the Promised Land of Canaan and emphasizes that full civic rights and land grants were given for those (Protestant males) who would come. A part of the text was especially dedicated to the amenities of the Carolinas for political asylum seekers, such as himself:

“Now many Germans, Swiss, expelled French, people from Piedmont and Salzburg as well as many Britons find themselves in Carolina and it is said in new and true reports that they live in good peace and enjoyment amongst each other, that they are thankful to God for His leading and governing and that they are serving Him better here than in the Old World. God has to be thanked that He showed His great mercy in giving the suffering people of Europe a medicine and a new paradise garden, which is a pantry of plenty and a homestead for many thousands.”²¹

As a result of the efforts, a group of ninety-nine persons from Appenzell Ausserrhoden were ready to migrate, many of them from Rehetobel. Arriving in South Carolina, the group would finally comprise about two hundred persons from different parts of the Swiss Confederacy, mainly from the eastern parts as the Rhine Valley or the Toggenburg. Whole families and pregnant women were part of the group. In the meantime, Bartholomäus Zuberbühler was able

²⁰ Kern, “Johannes Tobler,” 59-67; Virginia Bowe Strickland, *Five Fortune Tellers of New Windsor: Tobler, Zubly, Meyer, Sturzenegger and Nail, Swiss Pioneer Families of South Carolina* (Augusta: self-publishing, 2009), 4-12.

²¹ Johannes Tobler, “Kurtze Beschreibung der neuen Welt oder des grossen Welt-Theils America,” *Appenzeller Kalender* 15 (1736): without pagination. Translated from early modern German to modern English by the author.

to secure a land contract from the Governor of South Carolina, dated July 17, 1736. The government of Appenzell Ausserrhoden, on the other hand, did not want to let the group go and decreed that they had to leave half of their assets behind and that they would lose their citizenship permanently. However, this did not stop Johannes Tobler or the other members of the group.²²

Before leaving, Tobler handed over the editorship of the “Appenzeller Kalender” together with his calculations for the almanac for the following fifteen years to his confidant and fellow *Linden* Gabriel Walser (1695-1776), who was the priest of the parish of Speicher, a neighboring village to both Rehetobel and Trogen. The periodical was since then issued annually without a gap until today.²³

Johannes Tobler and his family left their home in late summer 1736, never to return. For unknown reasons, they left behind their ten-year old daughter Catharina (1727-1745)—she would receive 3,000 guilders when she married from money Johannes Tobler left with his father-in-law Bartholomäus Zellweger. Their route took them to the village of Horn on Lake Constance, where they boarded a ship. They had to change vessels in Schaffhausen, because of the Rhine Falls, before arriving in Basel. From there, the journey continued to Rotterdam on the Rhine River. Once there, a problem arose as the local authorities wanted to force the group to use a Dutch vessel for their transatlantic passage, when the Swiss group already had purchased passage on a British vessel. The ensuing quarrel led to a delay of six weeks and some expenses. Following an intervention by the British delegate in the Hague, the group was finally allowed to sail on the English vessel under one Captain Dunbarr.²⁴ Tobler summarizes the

²² Gabriel Walser, *Der Appenzeller-Chronick dritter Theil in welchem alle die vornehmste Begebenheiten so sich von An. 1732 bis An. 1763 sowohl inn- als ausser dem Land Appenzell zuge-tragen unpartheyisch beschrieben worden* (Trogen: Meyer und Zuberbühler, 1829), 150-51; Peter Witschi, *Appenzeller in aller Welt. Auswanderungsgeschichte und Lebensschicksale* (Herisau: Schläpfer, 1994), 138-40; Gilbert P. Voigt, “The German and German-Swiss Element in South-Carolina 1732-1752,” *Bulletin of the University of South Carolina* 113 (1922): 45.

²³ Witschi, *Appenzeller in aller Welt*, 138-41 and 263-64.

²⁴ Johannes Tobler, “Brief vom 12. September 1736,” in *Erstes Stück. Deren auß CAROLINA, eingesandten ausführlichen Nachrichten (...)*, ed. Bartholome Anhorn (St. Gallen: Anhorn, 1738), 9-15; Gilbert P. Voigt, “Swiss Notes on South Carolina,” *The South Carolina Historical and Genealogical Magazine* 21, no. 3 (1920): 93-104.

journey in a letter, where he also mentions a stopover in Falmouth in Cornwall:

“We sailed from Falmouth (where [I] wrote you also) the 5 December, & the night after had a severe storm, & that we did not see Carolina until the 25 January, & for the reasons stated arrived here safe and sound the 1st of January [February, D.A.], & that of more than 200 persons only three children & a half-grown [illegible] girl died, & that the sea causes me and my wife no vomiting, as also that my wife was afterwards delivered very safely and quickly of a daughter, both of whom are, praise God, well & hearty.”²⁵

With the birth of their tenth and last child Anna Maria (1737-1800), the Toblers began their new life in America.

Starting a Colonial Life

That Johannes Tobler and his group of Swiss migrants were allowed to settle in South Carolina as foreigners was part of a greater plot of the British colonial administration to secure and enlarge its backcountry against the Native inhabitants of the region, the French in the Mississippi Valley, and the Spanish presence to the south in Florida. Governor Robert Johnson (1682-1735) planned eleven defensive townships to that end, nine of which were realized. The only requirement for settlers was that they had to be Protestant. As this included dissenters and persecuted congregations from Europe, the South Carolina backcountry was settled by people belonging to a wide variety of Protestant congregations and sects. For many of the colonists, escaping poverty was the main reason for migration. As political refugees, Johannes Tobler and members of his group were rather the exception.²⁶

²⁵ Charles Guy Cordle, ed., *The John Tobler Manuscripts: An account of Swiss immigrants in South Carolina in 1737* (Augusta: unpublished manuscript, 1937), 5.

²⁶ Bruce R. Penner, “Old World Traditions, New World Landscapes: Ethnicity and Archaeology of Swiss-Appenzellers in the Colonial South Carolina Backcountry,” *International Journal of Historical Archaeology* 1, no. 4 (1997): 269-70; Voigt, “German-Swiss Element,” 5-20.

The colonial administration granted lands in the Indigenous territory to the settlers so that they could build settlements, towns, and infrastructure, thereby dispossessing the original inhabitants. They primarily sought to give out grants to larger groups as they had a better chance to establish themselves in the remote and rough environments—speaking from a coastal or European point of view. As those groups came from Europe, intermediaries were necessary who recruited them in Europe and brought them to South Carolina. People such as the aforementioned Sebastian Zuberbühler or Jean Pierre Pury thought of those enterprises as businesses since they had to fulfill their given quotas and were paid by the colonial government for their services. Of course, they did not write about this in their pamphlets.²⁷

The Swiss groups that were migrating to South Carolina, North Carolina, and Pennsylvania between 1680 and 1750 were part of the first larger migration wave between the Swiss Confederacy and America. The Swiss themselves were a minority in the group of German and French speaking migrants as there were, for example, also groups from Salzburg in Austria, the Palatinate, and different parts of France settling in the Carolina backcountry. And all of these groups were in language minorities themselves, since the majority of the European newcomers spoke English. However, the founding of Purrysburg in 1731/32 was not only the first settling of a Swiss group in the South Carolina backcountry but the first of a German or French speaking group, as well.²⁸

Skirmishes and full out wars with the Native inhabitants of the area were fought at the time Tobler arrived in South Carolina. Although already being diminished in great numbers by diseases brought from Europe, such as smallpox, the killings in the conflicts, and enslavement, the Indigenous landscape still was very much in existence. As many as twenty-nine distinct groups of Indigenous

²⁷ Leo Schelbert and Hedwig Rappolt, ed., *“Alles ist ganz anders hier” Schweizer Auswandererberichte des 18. und 19. Jahrhunderts aus dem Gebiet der heutigen Vereinigten Staaten* (Zurich: Limmat, 2009), 50-74.

²⁸ Gérald Arlettaz, “Emigration et colonisation suisses en Amérique,” *Studien und Quellen* 5 (1979): 32.

inhabitants, subdivided into the five language families of Siouan, Muskogean, Yuchi or Uchean, Algonquian and Iroquoian, lived in the area which the colonizers designated as South Carolina on their maps.²⁹

The Province of Carolina was founded in 1670, mainly by British sugar planters from the Caribbean who brought a great number of enslaved people with them. In fact, at the time Johannes Tobler arrived, there were more enslaved people of African descent living in the colony than those of European descent. The Carolinas in the time were an important place concerning the development of modern constitutions, as the philosopher John Locke (1632-1704) presumably was involved in writing the one of 1669. In the northern part of the territory, settlers poured in from other colonies such as Virginia and Pennsylvania. This led to the partition of the colony in 1712. In 1729, South Carolina came under direct rule of the British monarch George III, to strengthen his standing in the region. Charleston, the capital and main harbor of South Carolina (sometimes written Charlestown or Charles-Town in contemporary sources), had been founded in 1670 and had become one of the busiest ports in Colonial America at the time Johannes Tobler arrived.³⁰

It is pure luck that Johannes Tobler's diary from the time of his arrival in South Carolina has survived, since a great deal of his personal writing seems to have vanished. The diaries span the period from February 11 to March 17, 1737;³¹ the first weeks that the migrants spent in Charleston. The entry for Friday the eighteenth of February notes the oath the newly arrived from the Swiss Confederation had to take and about the land grants they received:

²⁹ Aram Mattioli, *Verlorene Welten: Eine Geschichte der Indianer Nordamerikas* (Stuttgart: Klett-Cotta, 2017), 33-40.

³⁰ David Armitage, "John Locke, Carolina, and the *Two Treatises of Government*," *Political Theory* 32 (2004): 602-27; Leo Schelbert, "The Enmeshment of Five Worlds, 1710-1713: The Making of New Bern in Southern Iroquoia," *Swiss American Historical Society Review* Special Edition (November 2010): 1-55.

³¹ The German original of the text seems to have vanished, although it is mentioned that it had been kept at some time in the State Library of Appenzell Ausserrhoden. Charles Guy Cordle, ed., "The John Tobler Manuscripts: An account of Swiss immigrants in South Carolina, 1737," *The Journal of Southern History* 5, no. 1 (1939): 83-97.

Figure 4: Map of Georgia and South Carolina from 1746 from a book by Samuel Urlsperger. Tobler's settlement of New Windsor would be opposite of Fort Augusta; further down the river the Swiss Colony of Purrysburg is shown. Public Domain.

“In the morning we went before the “Commissari” and had to take an oath for so long as we remain in the land, that we respect and regard the present king in England as the legitimate one, also his princes and princesses as the legitimate successors, and not the Pretender or another Catholic king; (...)”³² [We] would be permitted to go in the whole land wherever we pleased and, if we wished, to go out again. The land that is given us is 50 acres a head, for us and our posterity’s property. We might sell it, exchange it, in fact dispose of it at will as with our property. We enjoy every right, like born Englishmen. (...) They give us a certain quantity of provisions for a year, also implements and cattle; and [we] have to give nothing in return except we must give in turn to the servants the provisions which we [received] for the service years when their service years are up and they receive their own land. They give us a guide to the place, also expenses above the yearly [allowance]. Wife, children, and baggage will be brought to us afterwards by water as soon as we have declared where we wish to remain.”³³

Tobler, together with other members of his group, decided to go on a reconnaissance tour looking for suitable land in the townships of Amelia, Saxe-Gotha, and New Windsor.³⁴ He tells us of his preparations for this first tour inland in his diary on February 20:

“To-day [I] was asked to give 40 pounds for a strong but not fine 8 year old horse and believe that [I] shall take it to-morrow, because I find it hard to travel 150 miles on foot, and especially because I want to take along my daughter and a maid, who cannot walk all the time either. A fine outfit for horseback riding without cloak and boots cost me 40 pounds; yet saddle blanket and pistol holsters could not be made so neatly with you.³⁵ In short, everything here is very costly, partly because too many people arrive, [and partly because] on the other hand the transportation [is] too great, and the skilled workers [are] too

³² The Catholic James Francis Eduard Stuart (1688-1766) claimed the throne of England and Scotland and was called pretender by his enemies. Neil Oliver, *A History of Scotland* (London: Weidenfeld & Nicholson, 2009), 300-02.

³³ Cordle, *Tobler Manuscripts*, 10-1.

³⁴ Brent H. Holcomb, *Petitions for Land from the South Carolina Council Journals, Volume 1: 1734/5–1748* (Columbia: SCMAR, 1996), 85; Penner, “Old World Traditions,” 282.

³⁵ Meaning unclear.

few. Good artisans can here earn their piece of bread and much more besides.”³⁶

For some migrants within Tobler’s group the story goes otherwise. The policy of giving away free governmental aid for the newly arrived had changed in the very year they arrived—though they could still apply for a land grant. For many there was only the possibility to go into servitude for four to seven years (as the standard contracts stated) to pay for their passages and livelihoods. This was the fate of a fellow traveler of Tobler, Bernhard Trachsler from Elgg in the Canton of Zurich. He worked, among other occupations, as a butcher in Charleston and finally, after being released early out of his servitude via a court ruling, returned frustrated to the Swiss Confederacy. In 1742, he printed a short pamphlet in the form of a poem under Tobler’s name to advise his compatriots against migrating to South Carolina. For the longest time, this poem has been attributed to Johannes Tobler himself. Other reports from fellow travelers also warned the Swiss from going to America.³⁷

As a first stop on his reconnaissance tour, Johannes Tobler visited his father Ulrich in Orangeburg where he had left him nearly two years previously. He would come to live with his son and family, but died the year after. Johannes’ son Ulrich had already left for Charleston after receiving the news of his family’s arrival and they would meet after his father returned. Another son of Johannes, four-year-old Bartholomäus, had died in Charleston during his father’s absence.³⁸

The Swiss migrants, around twenty-five families from Tobler’s party, decided to settle in the township of New Windsor which had been established the very same year. The area lay by the Savannah River, even more upstream than Purrysburg. New Windsor was at the

³⁶ In the original text, the letter L stood in place of the word pound. Cordle, *Tobler Manuscripts*, 12.

³⁷ Anonymous, *Ein und Zwanzigstes Neujahrsblatt der Zürcherischen Hülfsgesellschaft. Für die menschenfreundliche Jugend unserer Vaterstadt. 1821* (Zurich: Zürcherische Hülfsgesellschaft, 1820), 3-23; Schelbert and Rappolt, *Alles ist ganz anders hier*, 94-115 and 165-177; Bernhard Trachsler, *Eine ausführliche Relation oder Beschreibung aus Carolina (...)* (Bern: Obere Druckerei, 1742), 1-4.

³⁸ Cordle, *Tobler Manuscripts*, 18-9.

time more a name on a map than a real settlement. However, within its perimeter lay Fort Moore which consisted of some twenty to thirty huts and a palisade. Fort Moore had been established in 1715, during the so-called Yamasee War, a conflict between the colonizers and different Indigenous groups that nearly ended Britain's foothold in this part of America. On the spot where Fort Moore was built there had previously been a settlement called Savaneton or Savanno Town. This settlement was a trade hub between the British and the Indigenous nations to the West since 1685. Right opposite the Savannah River lay Augusta, established a few years prior and also boasting a fortification. Today, the names New Windsor, Savaneton, and Fort Moore have ceased to exist, the towns of North Augusta and Beech Island are situated where New Windsor once was.³⁹

The area designated as New Windsor had, at the time, very much been part of an Indigenous landscape, although place names were not written down as thoroughly as in the colonial topography. Savaneton, however, was a name of Indigenous origin and was replaced by the name of New Windsor. Compared to the Native inhabitants, the newly arrived settlers were only a small group. Johannes Tobler came into contact with a local group of Chikasaws when he first arrived in New Windsor:

“As I wrote this, the king of the savages, together with four others, stood by me. [They] looked sharply at me and showed me the peace-treaty which they had made with the king in England; and after they had shown other signs of friendship & love, they bowed, offered me their hands, & took a courteous leave. They painted themselves strangely with red color. The king wore a beautiful brass breastplate over his heart. Moreover the people here are very friendly & do whatever they can to please us.”⁴⁰

³⁹ Harold S. Maness, *Forgotten outpost: Fort Moore & Savannah Town, 1685-1765* (Beech Island: BPB Publications, 1986), 111-33; Penner, “Old World Traditions,” 269-70.

⁴⁰ Tobler in his writings regularly calls the Native inhabitants of the Carolinas “savages,” which is a translation of the German term *Wilde*. For the leader of the Indigenous group, he uses the word “king,” which is a translation of a European concept onto this society. Cordle, *Tobler Manuscripts*, 15.

Taking possession of the land which was granted to Tobler by the King of England took place on the same day as meeting with the leader of the Chikasaws. However, this was an affair which was done wholly without the Indigenous population. Johannes Tobler describes the process which included a bit of bargaining:

“At 10 o’clock came 2 guides, one of whom spoke German. With them we traveled above [Savaneton] some miles toward the north. There, to be sure, we saw fairly good land, but not yet leasing to us & too far from the river. [We] said therefore that we did not like it, & if no better land & by the river was to be found, [we] would go back to another place. But because they were unwilling to let us go, they traveled with us below Savaneton (the foot people could not follow). As soon as we were 3 or 4 miles from the river, we were already seeing better land; and soon it appeared to us good enough.”⁴¹

The trope of the “maiden land” with its dense forests, etc., can be found in Tobler’s writings, as was fairly common in the time in these contexts, and contrary to the reality that the land had been settled by Native communities for centuries.⁴² However, even Tobler remarked that the land he now took possession of was in no way maiden:

“There are still some wretched huts there, which I suppose the savages once built, but now deserted. It may also be that Christians came & either died or otherwise deserted them. But they may be made by whomsoever they will, this great tract of lands belongs to us & those following [us] because only one man has had land surveyed there, so that consequently we are the first except for him.”⁴³

The appropriation of land in this citation is laid out very clearly. Tobler sees that the area had been part of a Native settlement

⁴¹ Ibid., 16.

⁴² Jürgen Osterhammel, *Die Verwandlung der Welt: Eine Geschichte des 19. Jahrhunderts* (München: C.H. Beck, 2009), 465-564.

⁴³ Cordle, *Tobler Manuscripts*, 19.

but denies that Indigenous people could even possess properties as they do not survey their lands, “so that consequently we are the first.”⁴⁴

Early modern contradictions

The start in this new environment was harsh for Johannes Tobler, his family, and his fellow settlers. About forty people died within the first year of their arrival due to sickness and deprivation. In a report written about fifteen years later, Tobler stated that only five German speaking families were living in New Windsor. Not much had been left of the settlers of the Swiss group, many of whom had moved to nearby Augusta or other places.⁴⁵ Tobler, on the other hand, built a livelihood in New Windsor. He published a text in the “Appenzeller Kalender” for the year 1753 where he describes his property and possessions:

“I for my part am doing well in my new beloved Fatherland and am content with the guidance of the Almighty. At the beginning, hard work, sense and sorrows, and many purchases and occurrences remarkably damaged my health and timely goods; but soon the Lord rewarded all my efforts with tenfold blessings. I owe now a spacious household, various good and comfortable houses, barns, huts, magazines full of products of the land and trading goods, farmhands, milkmaids, negroes, horses and cattle; I live on an elevated and healthy spot and rule like a Prince over a plot of arable land, which is over an hour long and half as wide; together with my elder son I run a large grocery store which contains also other wares, those we get in Savannah in exchange for grain etc. with the help of a curious ship which is 40 feet long and 6 feet wide and has 4 oars; what is more, I owe a spacious smithy, (...) Moreover, the Governor of this Province has assigned me for three years now the honorable but arduous position of the Royal Britannic

⁴⁴ This is interesting as it contradicts in a way the notion of John Locke that links the possession of land to labouring it. Armitage, “John Locke,” 602-27.

⁴⁵ Walter L. Robbins, ed., “John Tobler’s Description of South Carolina (1753),” *The South Carolina Historical Magazine* 71, no. 3 (1970): 150-51; Voigt, “German-Swiss Element,” 32.

Figure 5: Tobler's house and the surroundings in New Windsor on a plate from 1762, when he bequeathed a part of the estate to his son John. Courtesy: South Carolina Department of Archives and History, Columbia, S.C. (S213184, Colonial Plats, Volume 7, p. 278).

Justice of the Peace in Granville County;⁴⁶ an honor which before me no one has received who did not completely master the English language.”⁴⁷

Johannes Tobler had become wealthy and he had become a slave owner. As South Carolina was an infamous slaving colony (especially in the context of the sugar plantations in the coastal regions) and in that the first Swiss settlers in Purrysburg also had had slaves, this sadly comes as no surprise. However, in the context of Swiss history,

⁴⁶ Granville County was one of four districts into which South Carolina was subdivided by the time.

⁴⁷ Johannes Tobler, “Die Appenzeller in Nordamerika,” *Avisblatt von Herisau* 7 (1810): 52-3. Translated from early modern German to modern English by the author.

Tobler as a “man on the spot” who directly held enslaved people is an exception as the connection to the slave trade for the Swiss was above all indirect through investments.⁴⁸ Tobler first came into contact with enslaved people right after he left the ship in Charleston in 1737 and described his impressions:

“In other respects everything here is overcrowded with negroes, who as slaves do absolutely all work but look very wild and roguish, and [I] could not believe anything good of them. They bear very many children, who must also serve as slaves their whole life long. To my thinking, they live like cattle. In short, I do not like them, although they do not the least harm nor dare to, because they are forbidden under heavy penalty.”⁴⁹

In this and other citations in Tobler’s writing, general prejudices are reproduced and no empathy for the enslaved is to be traced, for example when he writes: “(...) for I would rather buy negroes than have anything to do with people who always want to get out of one’s control,”⁵⁰ or: “At present, you pay for one hundred acres of land, as well as for a Negro, only ten and one-half Batzen in your money.”⁵¹ We do not know how many enslaved people Johannes Tobler “owned” during his lifetime. Generally, there have been lower numbers of enslaved people in the South Carolina backcountry than in the lowlands with its big sugar plantations. And the era of cotton had not yet started.⁵² In his last will, the inventory lists two “chattel,” a woman, and a child. The woman probably was Tobler’s cook.⁵³ Tobler writes about church service for the enslaved in a report sent to Switzerland:

⁴⁸ Thomas David, et al., *Schwarze Geschäfte: Die Beteiligung von Schweizern an Sklaverei und Sklavenhandel im 18. und 19. Jahrhundert* (Zurich: Limmat, 2005), 15-121; Hans Fässler, *Reise in Schwarz-Weiss: Schweizer Ortstermine in Sachen Sklaverei* (Zurich: Rotpunkt, 2005), 17-27.

⁴⁹ Cordle, *Tobler Manuscripts*, 12.

⁵⁰ *Ibid.*, 5.

⁵¹ Robbins, “Tobler’s Description,” 161.

⁵² David Colin Crass, et al., “Excavations at New Windsor Township, South Carolina,” *Savannah River Archaeological Research Heritage Series* 3 (1997): 7-23.

⁵³ South Carolina Archives, *Inventory Book W*, 265-67.

“Now and then, people also work on [converting] the black slaves, and, in Carolina, many of them can be found who are baptized, and also a few among them who demonstrate their Christianity in their lives. My older son, when he is here (for he is often traveling), instructs the Negroes in Christianity every Sunday.”⁵⁴

Although New Windsor was situated right in the middle of Indigenous territory and Johannes Tobler probably profited largely from trading with the Natives, not very much is learned about the relationship of the Swiss settlers with the Natives from his writings. Concerning the general buildup of the trade and his opinion on the Natives,⁵⁵ Tobler remarks:

“From here and Augusta, every year, over 2,000 horses loaded with goods go up to 1,000 miles west into the Indian country, some of whom return once, some twice a year with deer skins. These are then sent in boats that carry up to 2,000 pounds, either to Savannah or, more commonly, to Charles-Town, and the boats return from there bringing all sorts of necessary goods. (...) The river is not navigable upstream from here, since there is a waterfall not far from here.”⁵⁶

“The Yuchi Indians when they come to us, prefer for us to give them rum and cinnabar, with which to paint their faces and other parts of their body, than for us to give them food and drink.”⁵⁷

“Otherwise, they are a bloodthirsty, warlike and malevolent people and treat their prisoners of war wretchedly. But they are kind toward people whom they meet on the road or in the woods; they show people, who have lost their way, the right way, and do not deny one anything, as long as they have something.”⁵⁸

During the so-called Cherokee War from 1759 to 1761, which was linked to the Franco-British Seven Years War, Johannes Tobler

⁵⁴ Walter L. Robbins, ed., “John Tobler’s Description of South Carolina (1753) (conclusion),” *The South Carolina Historical Magazine* 71, no. 4 (1970): 262-63.

⁵⁵ Urs Bitterli, “Der Eingeborene im Weltbild der Aufklärungszeit,” *Archiv für Kulturgeschichte* 53 (1971): 249-63.

⁵⁶ Robbins, “Tobler’s Description,” 149-50.

⁵⁷ Robbins, “Tobler’s Description (conclusion),” 264.

⁵⁸ *Ibid.*, 259.

built barricades around his estate and sheltered settlers from another district. His son Ulrich who was Captain in the militia at the time, was slain by Native people during this crisis on his way to Fort Moore. His brutal death was described in great detail in “The South Carolina Gazette” of February 23, 1760.⁵⁹

For the Protestant settlers, life revolved around church services, although there was no church building in New Windsor. As there was also a scarcity of preachers, Tobler wanted to underline in his report (which again also served as an advertisement for migration from Switzerland to South Carolina in the 1750s) that Sunday religious services were held regularly in his house:

“To be sure, a church service is held three times each Sunday according to the Swiss rites, however the sermons are only read aloud and the service is held in my house. But occasionally, my dear son-in-law, the Rev. Züblin, comes from Wando to us, along with others. He was with us all last March and preached, with much conviction, three times each Sunday, and during the week too, and did other things well befitting a true servant of Jesus Christ, in both the English and German languages. Because, as I have just said, he preaches in English, many English people come here on Sunday, so that my living room, spacious as a rule, can hardly contain them.”⁶⁰

Tobler’s house was a fitting place for worship as he owned the only house organ in the greater region. It is not clear if this is the same musical instrument he had owned in Rehetobel prior to his departure and taken with him or if he had bought a new one. In any case, Tobler tried to reestablish the intellectual life he had experienced in Appenzell Ausserrhoden. He collected and loaned books in German, for example from his “dear friend” Johann Martin Boltzius (1703-1763), the preacher of German origin in Ebenezer, with whom he also regularly corresponded. Johannes Tobler even

⁵⁹ Crass, *Excavations*, 71-2; Strickland, *Fortune Tellers*, 12; Daniel J. Tortora, *Carolina in Crisis: Cherokees, Colonists, and Slaves in the American Southeast, 1756–1763* (Chapel Hill: The University of North Carolina Press, 2015), 102-16.

⁶⁰ Robbins, “Tobler’s Description,” 151-52.

made inventions. He advertised in “The South Carolina Gazette” in 1744 that he had invented a rice cleaning machine out of which “three slaves can produce as much as three barrels of rice a day.” He also ordered a globe, books, and several almanacs from Switzerland. The South Carolina Encyclopedia concludes that “the Swiss patriarch brought a new level of culture to the colonial frontier.”⁶¹

Meanwhile in Switzerland, Gabriel Walser, the editor of the “Appenzeller Kalender,” ran out of the prefabricated calculations by his predecessor Tobler around the year 1750. Without asking Walser first, Tobler began new calculations for the meridian of Rehetobel and sent them to his successor, once again for the following fifteen years. Little did he know that a new calendar maker from Trogen, Ulrich Sturzenegger (1714-1781), had arisen and that he was negotiating with Walser to take over the “Appenzeller Kalender.” Sturzenegger already had issued an almanac with his calculations, since 1745, in Trogen under a different title. Walser accepted the offer in 1749, since he was moving from Speicher to Berneck in the Rhine Valley. Johannes Tobler wrote that he would not have made the effort to calculate fifteen more years for the Swiss almanac if he had known that Sturzenegger did the maths by himself. However, in the 1750s there followed two collaborative issues of the “Appenzeller Kalender” by Sturzenegger and Tobler, while Tobler edited two other Swiss almanacs which came out in St. Gallen. In them he printed lengthy descriptions of South Carolina and of his life there. Citations from these texts have been used widely in this article.⁶²

Johannes Tobler then planned to issue almanacs in his new home in America. There was a tradition of English-speaking almanacs in America since 1639. They became very popular in the eighteenth century with the general public and were widespread. However, all of them were produced in the intellectual centers such as Boston or Philadelphia, rather than in the south of the

⁶¹ Fritz Hamer, “Tobler, John,” South Carolina Encyclopedia, last modified August 26, 2022, <https://www.scencyclopedia.org/sce/entries/tobler-john/>; George F. Jones, “The Savannah River Intelligentsia: 1734-1780,” *Society for the History of the Germans in Maryland* 42 (1993): 30-8.

⁶² Aragai and Prohaska, *Der Appenzeller Kalender*, forthcoming.

Figure 6: Title page of “The South Carolina Almanack” for 1758. Johannes Tobler served as philomath for this title, the contents were put together by the printer Christopher Sower. Courtesy: South Carolina Historical Society.

Colonies.⁶³ Compared with the German almanacs Tobler was familiar with, the similarities of those almanacs outweighed the differences by far. In 1749, he announced in a local newspaper that a South Carolina Almanac by him would be published the following year. Due to unknown reasons this almanac was never printed. Then, two years later, the first “South-Carolina Almanack” appeared for the year 1752 under the anglicized name John Tobler. Apart from the preface of the 1755 edition, Tobler seems only

⁶³ There had been a local printing press for Benjamin Franklin’s *Poor Richard’s Almanack* from Philadelphia in Charleston since 1733, but no autonomous almanac. William Pencak, “Politics and Ideology in “Poor Richard’s Almanack,”” *The Pennsylvania Magazine of History and Biography* 2 (1992): 183-211.

to have served as the philomath of the almanac, so no texts were written by Tobler himself.⁶⁴

Like the “Appenzeller Kalender,” “The South Carolina Almanack” (later renamed as “The South Carolina and Georgia Almanack”) contained a *Calendarium* and a *Practica*. Compared to the Swiss product, the *Calendarium* in the American almanac had less religious content; for example, there were no name days of religious figures for each day. The *Practica* in the back of the almanac contained health and first aid recommendations, cooking recipes, directions for finding your way around South Carolina, news, and political articles. These contents were probably put together by the printer. For the first seven issues, the almanac was printed and edited in faraway Germantown near Philadelphia, by the German-American printer Christopher Sower (1721-1784). Sower previously had printed the first American almanacs in German for the diaspora community. This was probably why Tobler was familiar with him and printed his almanac (in English) with Sower. From 1758 onwards, “The South-Carolina and Georgia Almanack” was printed in Charleston.⁶⁵

Johannes Tobler now precalculated almanacs for nearly fifty years. This move led to the spreading of Tobler’s almanacs over a large part of the British Colonies. He offered them to any printer that would be interested in them:

“Since I by the Goodness and Assistance of the Most-High have finished my undertaken Kalender-Work for the Use of this Century, and one Year more, I thought it my Duty to give Notice of it to the Publick; They are all ready for the Press. If any Person should have a Mind to promote their Publication by taking upon him the Costs and Expenses required to their Printing, I am ready to serve him with some of them, or with

⁶⁴ Robert L. Meriwether, *The Expansion of South Carolina 1729-1765* (Kingsport: Southern Publishers, 1940), 68–9; Patrick Spero, “The Revolution in Popular Publications: The Almanac and New England Primer 1750-1800,” *Early American Studies* 8, no. 1 (2010): 41-74.

⁶⁵ York-Gothart Mix, “‘Ubi libertas, ibi patria’: Zur Interkulturalität deutschamerikanischer populärer Kalender des 18. und 19. Jahrhunderts,” in *Der Kalender als Fibel des Alltagswissens*, ed. York-Gothart Mix (Tübingen: Niemeyer, 2005), 43-56.

Figure 7: Title page of “The Pennsylvania Town and Country Man’s Almanack” for 1757, another one of Christopher Sower’s titles where Johannes Tobler served as philomath. Courtesy: Delaware Historical Society.

all, both in the German or English Language; I my self can not do it, because I live at too remote a Place from any Printing-Office, so that I cannot take due Care of it, and send them to those Places, where Almanacks be call'd for.”⁶⁶

This resulted in Tobler's name appearing on almanacs even after his death. This was explicitly mentioned in “The South-Carolina and Georgia Almanack for the year 1786” with the words: “By JOHN TOBLER, Esquire, And in his Life-Time calculated to the Year 1801.”⁶⁷

The first person to take on Tobler's offer was again Christopher Sower who published different almanacs every year. From 1754 to 1767, he printed “The Pennsylvania Town and Country Man's Almanack” under the name John Tobler. James Adams (1725-1792) in Wilmington took over from 1767 to 1777. It is especially important to note in this case that Johannes Tobler was not the author of the texts in the back of the almanac, as “The Pennsylvania Town and Country Man's Almanack” was highly political in spreading radical Whig ideas and promoting American Independence. Furthermore, the 1759 issue contained a long damnation of slavery and the 1764 issue an “Account of the prodigious Destruction of the Natives of America since the Settlement thereof by the Europeans.” The almanac turns out to be abolitionist and progressive in the century of enlightenment.

Other almanacs which used Tobler's calculations followed in the 1760s to the 1780s in New Jersey, Delaware, and Pennsylvania, all the way down to St. Augustine, Florida (this particular almanac was printed by his grandson David Zubly). In most of them, Tobler's name did not appear, as they were printed under pseudonyms such as Thomas Fox, Andrew Aguecheek (a character from Shakespeare's “Twelfth Night”), and others. Benjamin Franklin (1706-1790) was the most known philomath and editor of almanacs in Philadelphia, regularly publishing under the pseudonym Richard Saunders. In his

⁶⁶ Tobler, “Respective Reader,” without pagination.

⁶⁷ Sometimes these almanacs were falsely assigned to Tobler's son, but John jun. never was a philomath.

“Poor Richard improved” from 1761 to 1774 he used calculations by Tobler.⁶⁸

The transformation of Tobler’s calendar work from a European to an American context seems to be without disruptions from the very beginning, including the Americanization of his first name. This is also a hint of the strong influence of the editors and printers of the almanacs on the final product. It can also be seen as a transformation Tobler undertook when settling in America: in adopting new forms of expression and a new way of life. Johannes Tobler did not produce Swiss Almanacs in America, but very much American ones.

The title of this chapter reads “Early modern contradictions.” How could Tobler be a slave owner, an agent of colonization in an area where Indigenous people lived, and at the same time be an enlightened philomath, musician, and seemingly God-abiding man? To be a pious Protestant in the eighteenth century meant to acknowledge the divine order of the world. Everything was given by God and everything had its hierarchical place in this world according to God’s will. To amass wealth, to replace “heathen” Natives, to enslave “heathen” people far away from their homes, to repress women, everything—to put it simply—was explained and seen as God’s will. The contradictions we see today were not perceived as such in the early modern world. The debates on abolitionism, the idea of human rights, and women’s suffrage, among other issues, had only just begun but not primarily in Appenzell Ausserrhoden or the South Carolina backcountry. Johannes Tobler, who died on March 15, 1765, in New Windsor, did not have to deal with them.

Conclusion

Today, no people named Tobler from the lineage of Johannes are living in South Carolina anymore, since in the third generation after Johannes the last heir died without sons. However, through the

⁶⁸ The Library of Congress online catalogue lists the almanacs which were calculated by Johannes Tobler, albeit being published under a pseudonym. Library of Congress online catalogue, <https://catalog.loc.gov/vwebv/searchBrowse>, last visited September 14, 2023.

female line there are descendants of Johannes Tobler living in the area until today under different names. After two or three generations, all the Swiss settlers anglicized their names and forgot how to speak the language of their ancestors, since they were living in an Anglophone environment. No houses or landmarks of the period have survived. Archaeological diggings have been the only source to tap into the physical heritage of the Swiss settlers in the area.⁶⁹ So, is this story of Tobler's life without consequence? Probably not.

For way too long, Switzerland (and its historians) did not partake in the discussions about colonialism and slavery, since the Swiss Confederation never took possession of colonies. Swiss colonists however were aplenty in all corners of the world.⁷⁰ Johannes Tobler's story reminds us of this fact. Today, topics such as migration, slavery, and the destruction of Indigenous ecologies and lives are heatedly debated upon in the U.S.A., and not only among historians. Wounds inflicted many years ago are still hurting in the collective memory and the personal memories of the descendants of those involved. Johannes Tobler's story also reminds us of this.

*- David Aragai, M.A., *1986, is a historian based in Oberegg AI, Switzerland. His interests lie in the regional history of Appenzell, as well as the transnational entanglements of the Swiss.*

⁶⁹ Strickland, *Fortune Tellers*, 12.

⁷⁰ André Holenstein, et al., *Schweizer Migrationsgeschichte: Von den Anfängen bis zur Gegenwart* (Baden: Hier und Jetzt, 2018), 123-34.